

Thiopegan Derivatives : Part XXXV. A Study of the Reaction between 6-Amino Piperonal and Allyl Isothiocyanate

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Condensation of 6-amino piperonal and allyl isothiocyanate furnished N-2-aldehydo-4 : 5-methylenedioxy phenyl-N-allyl thiourea which has been cyclised to give 2-methyl-4-chloro-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene hydrochloride and 2-bromomethyl-4-bromo-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene by treatment with dry hydrochloric acid gas and bromine respectively. These products have been condensed with some amines to introduce basic side chains at position 4.

The introduction of halogen atoms and basic side chains is known to improve upon the pharmacological activity of the organic compounds. We report here the syntheses of thiopegan derivatives bearing these characters. For this purpose, an elaborate study of the reaction between 6-amino piperonal and allyl isothiocyanate which is in parallel with our

previous studies of the reactions of allyl isothiocyanate with anthranilic acid¹ and isatin² has been carried out.

Condensation of 6-amino piperonal (I) and allyl isothiocyanate (II) furnished N-2-aldehyde-4 : 5-methylenedioxy phenyl-N-allyl thiourea (III), which formed an oxime derivative. Further reactions with III, with probable mechanisms are given in charts I and II.

The product obtained from III after treatment with HCl analysed for $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2SCl_2$. The structure, 2-methyl-4-chloro-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene hydrochloride (IV) has been assigned as this product gave CO_2 and AgCl with aqueous solutions of Na_2CO_3 and $AgNO_3$ showing the presence of HCl and it also condensed, with only one molecular proportion of the amines showing that only one Cl atom that condenses with amines is bound with the system. This property has been employed for getting 2-methyl-6 : 7-methylene dioxy-10 : 11-thiopegan derivatives containing basic chains (V, Table I) for evaluating their antibacterial properties.

For introducing bromine atoms in the system, the following route has been worked up.

The product obtained from III by bromination was assigned the structure 2-bromo-methyl-4-bromo-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene (VII)¹. The presence of both the Br atoms in the system is supported by the condensation of this product with two molecules of piperidine to furnish 2-piperidinomethyl-4-piperidino-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene (VIII).

Antibacterial activity : (IV) was found to be active against *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Shiga* upto a dilution of 1 : 5000. III and V ($R = C_5H_{10}$) were active against *S. typhi*, *S. paratyphi*, *S. Schottmuelleri*, *Sh. dysenteriae*, *Shiga*, *B. subtilis* and *M. pyogenes*, var

1. K. S. Dhama, M. S. Atwal and H. S. Sachdev, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **14**, 304.

2. G. M. Sharma, K. K. Soni and K. S. Narang, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 1019.

aureus in 1 : 5000 dilution. (V, R = $-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$) and (V, R = $\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) have been found to be active against *B. subtilis* upto a dilution of 1 : 5000 and 1 : 1000 respectively.

TABLE I

2-Methyl-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopegan derivatives containing basic side chains at position 4

S.No.	Amine used	Product (V)	% Yield	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analytical results	
						Found %	Required %
1.	<i>n</i> -Butylamine	$-(\text{CH}_2)_3\cdot\text{CH}_3$	58	230	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$	C, 59.75	60.19
						H, 6.19	6.58
						N, 12.99	13.16
						S, 10.17	11.03
2.	Aniline	$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	66	142-43	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$	N, 12.53	12.38
3.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3(\text{m})$	25	189-90	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$	N, 11.93	11.90
4.	Ethanolamine	$-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{OH}$	70	238-39	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$	N, 14.71	14.43
5.	Piperidine	$-\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}$	87	210	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{S}$	N, 12.63	12.71
6.	Morpholine	$-\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}$	86	218	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_3$	N, 12.38	12.61

All these products were crystallised from ethanol.

EXPERIMENTAL*

1. *N*-2-Aldehyde-4 : 5-methylenedioxyphenyl *N*-allyl thiourea (III) : A mixture of allyl isothiocyanate (1.0 g., 0.01 mole) and 6-amino piperonal (1.7 g., 0.01 mole) was heated on a steam bath. It melted but solidified after about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and was heated for 3 hr. more. The product was cooled, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid as well as ethanol as yellow shining flakes, m.p. 255° (0.9 g., 30%). Fractional crystallisations from ethanol as well as acetic acid did not furnish any second product. Elution of the crude product with acetic acid also furnished a product (m.p. 245-48°), sufficiently pure for further use. Found : C, 54.21, H, 4.07, N, 10.47, S, 12.53, Calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{S}$: C, 54.54, H, 4.54, N, 10.61, S, 12.05%.

2. *Oxime of (III)* : A solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.7 g., 0.01 mole) and sodium acetate (0.8 g., 0.01 mole) in minimum quantity of water was added to a suspension of III (2.6 g., 0.01 mole) in water (10 ml.). It was heated on a water bath at 60-70° for 8 hr. The suspension did not go in solution completely but the colour changed from yellow to green. It was cooled and the product was obtained in approximately quantitative yield. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished greenish yellow needles, m.p. 208°. Found : N, 15.29; Calc. for : $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}$; N, 15.05%.

* Analyses are by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford, and Mr. B. N. Anand, Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh.

3. *2-Methyl-4-chloro-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene hydrochloride (IV)* : Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through a refluxed solution of N-2-aldehydro-4 : 5-methylenedioxyphenyl-N-allyl thiourea (III, 3.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml.). Within 5 minutes, an orange coloured solid separated which, however, dissolved after about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The passage of the gas was continued for another 3 hr. It was cooled and the product which had separated was collected. It was crystallised from acetic acid as orange coloured shining flakes, m.p. 220°.

The above filtrate on dilution with anhydrous ether, deposited a second crop of the same product as confirmed through undepressed mixed melting point. The combined yield was 2.7 g. (75%). Found : C, 45.21, H, 4.05, N, 8.82, S, 10.06, Calc. for $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2SCl_2$, C, 45.14, H, 3.76, N, 8.82, S, 10.0%.

4. *2-Methyl-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-enes containing basic side chains at position 4 (V, Table I)* : To a suspension of 2-methyl-4-chloro-6 : 7-methylene dioxy-10 : 11 thiopega-2-ene-hydrochloride (IV) in anhydrous ethanol was added an amine (3 equivalents). The clear solution obtained in each case after the addition of the amine was refluxed on a water bath for 5-6 hr. After the removal of ethanol, the residue in each case was treated with water. The products collected after repeated washings with water were purified. The data regarding these compounds is given in Table I.

5. *2-Bromomethyl-4-bromo-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene (VII)* : N-2-aldehydro-4 : 5-methylenedioxyphenyl-N-allyl thiourea (III, 2.6 g., 0.01 mole) was dissolved in acetic acid (30 ml.) and bromine (0.5 ml., 0.01 mole) taken in the same solvent (8.0 ml.), was added gradually at 60°, with continuous shaking of the reaction mixture, during 15 min. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 4-5 hr. and was diluted with anhydrous ether (50 ml.). The brown sticky product which became crystalline on trituration was collected (2.0 g., 52%). Crystallisation from acetic acid gave orange coloured rectangular plates, m.p. 235°. Found : C, 35.29, H, 2.89, N, 6.90, S, 7.8. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}N_2SBr_2O$: C, 35.37, H, 2.95, N, 6.9, S, 7.9%.

6. *2-Piperidinomethyl-4-piperidino-6 : 7-methylenedioxy-10 : 11-thiopega-9-ene (VIII)* was obtained in 65% yield by the condensation of VII with piperidine by a procedure identical with the one adopted in expt. 5 for the condensation of (IV) with various amines. It was crystallised from ethanol as light brown elongated needles, m.p. 215°. Found : N, 14.08. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{30}N_4O_2S$; N, 13.52%.